

EVALUATION OF KENAF (*HIBISCUS CANNABINUS L.*) COLLECTION SAMPLES FOR EARLY MATURITY AND PLANT HEIGHT

D.X. Xalikulov¹, M.V. Turdaliyev², M.X. Talebayeva³

PhD, Head of department at Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources¹

Master student of Tashkent State Agrarian University²

Bachelor student of Tashkent State Agrarian University³

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15876383>

Abstract. *The article presents the results of research on early maturity and plant height of non-traditional kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus L.*) accessions. The studies were conducted in 2024 at the experimental field of the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources. Fifty-eight hemp collection samples available in the National Genebank were studied. According to phenological observations, 25 accessions were evaluated as early-maturing, with a period from emergence to full maturity ranging from 117 to 127 days. Analysis of plant height showed that all 58 accessions belonged to the tall group (over 3.5 m) with an average height of 440.6 cm.*

Keywords: *research, accessions, early maturity, plant height, kenaf, variety.*

Introduction. Kenaf is a relatively new crop for our republic Uzbekistan. In 1990, kenaf was planted on 15,000 hectares in our republic. In 2022, kenaf was cultivated on 155,876 hectares worldwide, with a total yield of 246,461.3 tons. [1.]

Kenaf belongs to the group of valuable fiber crops. Its bast fibers make up 30% of the stem's mass, with the fiber itself accounting for 24%. The fibers are strong, soft, and hygroscopic, making them suitable for producing tarpaulins, sacks, carpets, ropes, furniture fabrics, and similar items. Its seeds contain 20% oil, widely used in leather tanning, soap making, and the paint and varnish industries. The oilcake serves as both fertilizer and animal feed. Stem residues are utilized in the paper and construction industries. Kenaf is native to South America and is cultivated in India, China, African countries, America, and Southern European countries.

Experimental Results: Scientific research was conducted in 2024 at the field experimental station of the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources. Field experiments were carried out according to the methodologies for conducting field trials established by the Uzbekistan Scientific Research Institute of Cotton (UzPITI) in 2007. During the research, 58 kenaf accessions were planted and comprehensively studied. These accessions, introduced from various countries and preserved in the National Genebank, possess valuable economic traits and characteristics. The main objective was to identify promising genotypes among these accessions that are best adapted to regional conditions and exhibit high performance indicators. The results of these studies are expected to enhance the importance of kenaf in our country's agriculture and expand its cultivation area.

Kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus L.*) is an annual herbaceous plant belonging to the mallow family (Malvaceae J.). Its seeds begin to germinate at 10-12°C, and viable seedlings emerge at 13-15°C. Mass germination of seedlings is observed at 20-22°C. The optimal temperature for kenaf growth and high yield formation is 23-25°C. Its heat requirement decreases towards the end of the growing season. Seed ripening can occur even at 14-16°C, by which time the air becomes relatively dry. [2].

Kenaf grows very slowly during the first 30-45 days of its growth period. During this time, its root system develops well. Afterward, its above-ground biomass increases rapidly, growing by 6-10 cm per day. Stem growth almost stops with the formation of narrow, lanceolate leaves. Protecting the kenaf from weeds is crucial during the initial slow growth phase of the stems. Kenaf's flowering period can last up to 6 weeks, with 1-2 flowers opening daily. In Uzbekistan's conditions, secondary and tertiary flowers can also form from the leaf axils, leading to 5-7 flowers opening per day. Kenaf is primarily self-pollinating, with limited cross-pollination sometimes observed. Flowers typically open in the morning, with cloudy weather delaying their opening. Flowers remain open for a short time, wilting and closing in the afternoon. Due to the extended flowering period, the ripening of bolls and seeds takes a long time. While seeds in the lower bolls ripen, flowering continues in the upper part of the stem. Technical maturity is observed in 110-130 days, while biological maturity (seed ripening) occurs in 130-150 days.

According to phenological observations, the developmental stages during the growing period of 58 kenaf accessions were recorded as follows: The emergence date was May 5–6, flowering occurred between July 4–17, and maturation was observed from August 30 to September 14. The period from emergence to full maturity ranged from 117 to 131 days, with an average duration of 128 days. Out of the total samples, 25 hemp accessions matured earlier than the average of 128 days and were therefore classified as early-maturing accessions (Picture 1.).

Picture 1. Quantity of kenaf accessions by growing period.

For plants cultivated for fiber extraction from their stems, plant height is a crucial factor for their growth, development, and yield. This has several important aspects:

- taller plants intercept sunlight more effectively, which is vital for the photosynthesis process.
- the fibers in taller plants are also longer and stronger. This increases the tensile strength of the fibers, making them better raw material for industry.
- taller plants typically have more fiber, allowing for a greater fiber yield during harvest.
- tall plants usually develop a deeper root system, which results in better acquisition of water and nutrients.

The height of the kenaf plant is a crucial parameter that determines its yield, product quality, and cultivation characteristics. It's directly linked to the plant's genetic properties, growing conditions, and cultivation objectives. The kenaf plant grows intensively at an optimal temperature of 25°C, with sufficient nutrients in the soil, during long daylight hours, and with regular irrigation.

In 2024, the height of the 58 kenaf accessions planted in the field experimental plot ranged from 377 to 490 cm, with an average of 440.6 cm (Picture 2.).

Picture 2. Plant height of kenaf accessions.

When plant height was analyzed by grouping, no short-stemmed (1.5-2.0 m) or medium-stemmed (2.5-3.0 m) accessions were identified. All 58 accessions were classified as tall-stemmed (taller than 3.5 m). This indicates that all accessions planted this year belong to the long-stemmed group (Picture 3.).

Picture 3. Kenaf accessions: Plant height by group.

Conclusions. Research aimed at determining the early-maturing characteristics of non-traditional kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus L.*) accessions identified a total of 25 accessions as early-maturing genotypes, which were evaluated as promising. These genotypes are distinguished by their quicker adaptation to regional climatic conditions and a shorter vegetation period, making them a valuable resource for breeding programs.

When analyzing the plant height of non-traditional kenaf accessions by grouping them into short-stemmed, medium-stemmed, and long-stemmed categories, it was determined that all 58 observed accessions belonged to the long-stemmed group (over 3.5 meters). This indicates that these kenaf genotypes possess high growth potential, making them promising raw material sources for fiber production. The data obtained are crucial for breeding efforts aimed at developing tall varieties.

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